

DO2 report for Dellinger project

Draft: DO2 report
v0.1, Mar 14, 2017
v0.2 Apr 23, 2017
Final 2 May 2017

Background

Delivery Object 2 is the resource exchange technical analysis component of the Phase 1 part of the Dellinger project. The initial approach chosen was to consider the technical aspects of projects, from application for access to the computational research infrastructure, account creation, user support and pilot project completion. This approach addressed the general use case associated with supporting research projects and did not explicitly consider the high level long term use case of interactions and communications between the national providers for future system acquisitions and support.

The process used for the DO2 report was to carry out a set of discussions with the project members from the national providers for their respective sites, formulate a draft report and then discuss the report address additional topics during weekly videoconference meetings. The concept of addressing short term, low volume projects as a viable mechanism emerged from the discussions with the members of the project group on possible approaches for supporting research projects. The most significant change was the inclusion of a process for gaining direct experience through the inclusion of low volume short term pilot projects to complement the larger use cases, e.g. NLPL.

This is complementary to the NLPL project, which is a longer term, high volume use case. The short term low volume use case also addresses a range of research projects that are not appropriate for consideration by other international mechanisms, such as PRACE DECI, but might be viewed as an early precursor for researchers who may wish to later propose to such international mechanisms.

The report has been reviewed by the project members and is considered to be accurate as of the writing of the report.

Statement of Delivery Object from the Project Directive

Delivery object 2: Resource exchange technical analysis

Delivery date: Steering group meeting Apr/May 2017.

Content: Technical outline for resource sharing between countries, including user support.

Recipient: The national providers and NeIC.

Delivery process: Delivery is a document that describes an acceptable technical framework that enables resource sharing and will include the identification of technical issues and potential approaches to resolving them. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

Technical outline of the processes

The identification of technical issues was undertaken by discussing the processes at each site that are necessary to support the life cycle of a research project at the national providers. This included the major steps of applying for access, setting up the necessary accounts, providing user support during the research project, and closing down the access at the conclusion of the allowed access period.

The following sections provide specific information on each partner for each of the four basic steps,

- Applying for access.
- Account creation for allocated access
- User support
- Access termination and project close out

Applying for access

	Mechanism	Anticipated work required
Denmark	Allocations are done in periods of four months (Mar-Jun, Jul-Oct, Nov-Feb). Danish researchers can apply via the web form https://abacus.deic.dk/get-access/call-for-access Other academic researchers and non-academic use applies via email (paid). Due dates: 1 ½ month before period startdate. PI requirements: None	Commitment to provide access has been made for the initial short term low volume pilots. Information on the application process will need to be included in a common project website.
Finland	Academic researchers from Finland don't need to apply for access. Academic researchers outside Finland, who collaborate with a Finnish research group, apply with a free-form application to resource@csc.fi . Other academic researchers from abroad can get access only through international collaboration projects. Non-academic use is based on paid contracts.	Information on the application process will need to be included in a common project website. CSC customer management and resource allocation people need to be made known about which customer projects will be carried out at CSC.

Iceland	Academic researchers both inside and outside Iceland, who collaborate with a Icelandic research group, apply with a free-form application to support-hpc@hi.is .	Information on the application process will need to be included in a common project website.
Norway	Request submitted to: metacenter.no project manager process, Feide account Due dates: PMs get an email to let them know that there is an application due date. Information is distributed by email lists or announcements on the sigma2 website. No default resource allocation on Sigma2 resources. User can ask for a local account on local clusters by e-mail. PI requirements: Postdoctoral fellow or permanent position URLs: https://www.sigma2.no/content/who-can-apply	Information on the application process will need to be included in a common project website. Researchers are expected to apply through the Norwegian national process.
Sweden	Request submitted to: SNIC User and Project Repository (https://supr.snic.se/). Due dates: A specific round in SUPR would be created for a pilot. PI requirements: SNIC has “Small”, “Medium” and “Large” allocation rounds. For the specific pilot round the allocation size corresponds to SNIC Medium allocations, which requires the PI to be a Associate Professor. co-PI requirements: A PI may add co-investigators to a project. Co-investigators may be foreign researchers. URLs: (https://supr.snic.se/).	

Account creation process for access

	Mechanism	Anticipated work required
Denmark	Accounts for users are created using EduGAIN. The PI can invite other users to his project. Users which cannot use EduGAIN are created manually (The PI must provide a list to the NP).	If the users can use EduGAIN, everything is automatic. In some cases EduGAIN does not provide enough information on the user or EduGAIN is not available, in these cases users must be created

		manually.
Finland	Academic researchers from Finland get user accounts through a self-service portal (https://sui.csc.fi). Academic researchers outside Finland, who collaborate with a Finnish research group, get accounts based on information given in application forms. For international collaboration projects there is a named contact person who arranges accounts and resources for the customer projects. Paying customers get accounts based on information given in contract forms.	Requests for user accounts should have enough information so that the accounts can be created and associated with the right customer project.
Iceland	Users are created locally on the hpc clusters. An applicant must have a tenured position at an academic institution or an employee at a research institution in Iceland. A student is sponsored by the professor. A post-doc may have the requirement relaxed. A user applies electronically for access.	Accounts are verified and created by the hpc support team.
Norway	A user applies electronically for access: https://www.metacenter.no/mas/saml2/login/?next=/mas/ This requires a Feide login to apply. https://www.sigma2.no/content/call-e-infrastructure-resources-20171 co-PI:	The creation of the account: https://www.metacenter.no/user/application/ A user account can only be created after the user application form has been received and provided information is verified by both UNINETT Sigma and the project manager. Each new user account requires a separate form.
Sweden	An applicant would be required to create an account at SUPR. To be able to apply for and receive allocations on SNIC resources the applicant must be affiliated to a, by the Swedish research Council approved, custodian of funds, which includes academia and research institutes. Furthermore, applicants need to fulfil the requirements in terms of position, i.e. doctoral student, professor et.al. that is required for a specific type of allocation of compute time.	Applicants to SUPR would, in Swedish participation in a pilot, be required to register in an account in SUPR and in the process approve the SUPR user agreement, which defines the rights and obligations of the researcher.

User support process

	Mechanism	Anticipated work required
Denmark	Email to a email list support@deic.sdu.dk	Information on the support process will need to be included in a common project website.
Finland	The primary point of contact in case of problems, questions and requests is the CSC Service Desk, who can be contacted by email at servicedesk@csc.fi or by phone at +358 94572821.	Information on the support process will need to be included in a common project website.
Iceland	Email to an email list (support-hpc@hi.is) that goes into a ticket system.	Information on the support process will need to be included in a common project website.
Norway	Email to an email list (support@) that goes into a ticket system. Separate queues for the different hpc systems. Advanced user support (more than 1 weeks support to get the work done, software suite installation) is through the support email list. Application experts (Chemistry, CFD, ..). Discussions about structuring advanced application support but not currently in place.	Information on the support process will need to be included in a common project website.
Sweden	Contacts to the SNIC partner centers, should an applicant have questions about getting access to or running on a resource at a center. For the pilot this would be one of the support e-mails at each SNIC site.	

Access termination and close out process

	Mechanism	Anticipated work required
Denmark	User accounts automatically expire a week after the project's resources (node hours & disk space) expire	Information on the close out process will need to be included in a common project website.
Finland	Processes for managing life cycles of user accounts and customer projects are under automatisation. Probably the accounts and the projects will be set to expire in 1–2 years if not renewed. Until this is done, accounts and projects are	Information on the close out process will need to be included in a common project website.

	closed manually when their time is up.	
Iceland	The hpc support team terminates accounts.	Information on the close out process will need to be included in a common project website.
Norway	<p>User responsibility to clean up and move data, and a time out is set on the user account. The user gets a reminder email that the account will be terminated.</p> <p>Currently no active deletion of the data but may be purged if needed. Data in the home area is backed up and retained for a year or more. Local user admin may allow access later if requested through local user support system. Work areas are not backed up and may be purged after 3-4 weeks if space is needed.</p> <p>Project areas not yet operational. A user may be on multiple projects with a single user account.</p> <p>No policy in place for removing the data, it is done when needed.</p> <p>For a user having a 2 years break, user ID (integer) will be different, username may be the same.</p> <p>National policy for having same ID across all centers. One can request the user name of their own choice, if not granted based on name and surname.</p>	Information on the close out process will need to be included in a common project website.
Sweden	<p>Projects have a limited project period. SNIC Centers have the right to remove a user account which is no longer associated with a valid project after a waiting period of six months. This will include deletion of all data on SNIC storage resources which are tied to the aforementioned user account.</p> <p>(https://supr.snic.se/public/user_agreement/)</p>	

Technical issues or other concerns that have been identified

In the discussions that have taken place, it has become clear that the issues that must be addressed are primarily policy or process based. The process of setting up the low volume short term approach is expected to confirm the experience of the NLPL use case, for which accounts are in place in Norway and Finland and the researchers are active.

Sweden is currently acting as an observer and specific information is not included in this DO. There are no known technical issues that would prevent Sweden's full participation in Phase 2.

Appendix A: Approach based on short term, low volume projects

Dellingr has the capability to address short-term, low volume needs (= low CPU-quota). This would necessarily have a very low threshold for entry and provide quick turnaround for review. An example would be a student doing a master thesis which at most will need 50000-100000 CPU-hours during a 3-6 months period. It is complementary to the small type allocations that are offered by some of the national providers and the information requested from the PIs for this process is based on the information needed by several of the national providers for their small allocations.

Functional description of the low volume short term pilot process

The following is the functional description for accomplishing the necessary steps to set up and operate a resource sharing process to support the low volume short term pilots. There is an explicit goal of keeping this as simple as possible.

1. The national providers (NP) volunteer an amount of their Tier-1 resources to be shared with researchers in the Nordics
 - a. Provision of is voluntary and all researchers will have access, regardless of the whether their national provider (NP) is contributing
 - b. Ideally, the contributions should be in proportion to the overall commitments by each NP to the overall project
 - c. Allocations are considered to be equivalent to usage by the researchers
 - d. There should be no long term imbalance between allocations and commitments for a country
2. The shared resources are divided between the projects
 - a. The Project Group (PG) will ensure that the processes used to allocate access to the resources are consistent with national norms
 - i. This may be through the set of PG representatives for each contributing partner or by redirection to a national allocation process
 - ii. The representatives may refer applications to established researchers with expertise in different fields of science, e.g., physics, chemistry, bioscience if additional review is needed
 - b. Each project has a principal investigator (PI) associated to NP
 - i. PI applies for the resources
 - ii. The resources used by the PI are deducted from the total from the NP which PI is associated with
 - iii. PI defines the project members eligible to use the resources (users)
 - c. If the PG defines the allocations for the projects for the proposals submitted by PIs:
 - i. The proposal should consist of:
 1. Contact info and CV of PI, including publications

2. Project description (short), including the list of participants
3. Requested project resources and other requirements, such as application codes
- d. User account creation
 - i. PI provides the NP for which the project has resources with the list of users belonging to the approved project
 - ii. NP uses the method of own choice to authenticate the users, e.g., eduGAIN in Denmark, HAKA in Finland, Feide in Norway, direct in Iceland
 - iii. NP uses method of own choice to create accounts
- e. Tracking of allocations
 - i. Dellinger project group handles the process of aggregation of the allocation data for all projects and dissemination of this to the NPs
 - ii. NP is in charge of any necessary accounting for the projects for their own national purposes
 1. NP uses the method of own choice for accounting
3. Mapping of resource levels/allocations
 - a. The baseline assumption is that 1 CPU hour is the same across all CPUs
 - b. The metrics for mapping of other resources will need to be determined in Phase 2
 - i. Dellinger project group is to provide the SG with recommendations
4. User support
 - a. NP assumes that the user support is provided for the projects in the same way as it is provided for any other national project
 - b. NP uses ticket tracking system of own choice for tracking user issues
 - c. Collaboration between the NPs is encouraged in supporting the users
5. Cybersecurity
 - a. NP is responsible for the cybersecurity
 - b. List of security contacts is provided by the NP to assure the possibility to react in case of accidents, e.g., compromising the account at one site

This has entailed the design of a webpage, <https://blindij.github.io/> and an associated typeform submission page.

Contributions from each national provider:

National provider/system	CPU hours	Start date	End date	Allocation mechanism	User support mechanism

DeIC/Abacus 2.0	1,200,000 total	Mar 2017 Jul 2017 Nov 2017	Jun 2017 Oct 2017 Feb 2017	Project group	National
CSC/Sisu	300,000		Aug 2017	Project group	National
RHnet/Garpur	100,000			Project group	National
Sigma2/TBD	NLPL, others TBD			National	National
Sweden	Not applicable				

As additional information to encourage new users, a list of software resources available has been defined as the most commonly used applications packages available through the national providers. Other software packages may be supported at each of the national providers but are not included in this list.

Denmark	NAMD		Gromacs					
CSC	NAMD	GPAW	CP2K	Open-FOAM	VASP	Gaussian	Vlasior	Turbomole
Iceland	VASP	GPAW	Gromacs					
Norway	VASP	CCSM	Gaussian	Bifrost	LAMMPS	Dalton	Atlas	NAMD
Sweden								

Appendix B Approach based on a long term pilot project, the NLPL use case

The Nordic Language Processing Laboratory, NLPL, is an established long term pilot project that is described at

https://wiki.neic.no/wiki/Nordic_Language_Processing_Laboratory as:

“Our vision is to implement a Nordic virtual laboratory for Natural Language Processing by piloting innovative ways to share HPC and data resources across country borders, by pooling competency in expert support teams and within the user community, and by enabling internationally competitive, data-intensive research and experimentation.”

The project includes researchers from Denmark, Finland, Norway, and Sweden and resource commitments from national providers in Finland and Norway. It is a three-year project that will result in the creation of a shared ‘virtual laboratory’, comprising among other things a set of tools for machine translation, dependency parsing, hosting of appropriate textual data corpora, mechanisms for evaluation of the effectiveness of the core NLP models, and community formation and outreach mechanisms. The environment is to be used by this research group and is also planned to be available to other researchers in (large-scale) language processing.

NLPL	Number of researchers & accounts needed	Number of developers	Allocation commitments & type
Denmark	5-10	2-3	shown interest, but no contact established yet
Finland	10-15	4-6	up to 3000k hours per year on Taito
Iceland	-	-	not a partner in the consortium
Norway	10-15	6-7	500k hours on Abel in the period October 2016 - March 2017, 500k hours on Abel in the period April - September 2017
Sweden	10-15	7-8	no

NLPL experience from applying for resources from Finland and Norway

In the first few months of 2017, NLPL partners have obtained user accounts and computing and storage allocations on both Taito and Abel (and NorStore, <https://www.sigma2.no/content/storage-hardware-resources>). While some project members were active users of at least one of these systems before, some 15–20 new accounts had to be created on each system. At present, not only the user management structures but also the mechanisms used to grant allocations to individual users are fundamentally different for the two systems.

For Abel, new users requested their accounts and association with the NLPL Notur and NorStore projects on-line; for Taito, users from outside of Finland had to submit a scanned application form, to request both a project (typically one per NLPL member site) and a set of associated accounts. Fortunately, new user applications were processed smoothly on both sides, and accounts were usually available within a day or two after the original request was submitted.

For the Norwegian systems, allocations are managed by Stephan Oepen (who also originally initiated the NLPL collaboration) as the principal investigator for allocations NN9447K (Notur) and NS9052K (NorStore). Oepen was familiar with the application and allocation mechanisms from before, and communication with the Sigma2 administration and allocation committee has been smooth - including a consensual reduction of the NLPL application for the current application period (April 1 – September 30, 2017) after it emerged that computing demands have lagged behind original projections in the early phase of the project, in part due to delays in software installations: of 500k requested hours in the preceding allocation period, the project had only used about 30%. All NLPL users are associated to these Notur and NorStore allocations, i.e. they both enjoy the privilege of having access to the full NLPL allocations and the responsibility of needing to share these allocations with each other fairly. At least while usage on Abel is still building up, there is no practical concern about fairness of sub-allocation among NLPL users, and in general the project operates on the optimistic assumption that its total computing demands in the foreseeable future (of, say, somewhere between 2–5 million hours per year, towards the end of the NLPL project period) will be well within the bounds of available resources. Through the Sigma2 project administration interface, Oepen monitors usage on these projects and expects to report to the NLPL Steering Group regularly.

For the Finnish systems, the CSC representative in the NLPL Steering Group (Martin Matthiesen) has been very supportive, and much as in the case of Abel there is a general perception of ‘good-will’ support towards the NLPL initiative from CSC staff. Matthiesen suggested that each NLPL site acquire their own Taito project, and

allocations to these have been continuously made by CSC. The mid-term goal is to view this collection of allocations as one NLPL project group and regularly provide updates on user associations and resource usage to the Steering Group. Parallel to these computing projects, CSC granted a storage allocation of 25 gbytes (on Taito) to NLPL, and the Steering Group decided to also let Oepen act as the principal investigator for this storage project (intended to host project-specific software and data below ‘/proj/nlpl/’ on Taito, to mirror to the largest possible degree ‘/projects/nlpl/’ on Abel).

In conclusion, NLPL (with friendly support from the Norwegian and Finnish administrators) has succeeded in granting research staff at all partner sites access and allocations on both systems. However, the process was perceived as somewhat long-winded and lacking in uniformity by several users, e.g. with regard to different application and allocation regimes as well as to account naming and password conventions.

Likewise, it would be desirable for the NLPL Steering Group to keep up-to-date (preferably through a programmatic interface) about users associated with NLPL allocations and resource usage, e.g. to maintain NLPL-internal mailing lists and to inform future allocation requests; this will be a topic of growing importance in the next six to twelve months.

Finally, it remains a bit of an open question how to relate NLPL activity to pre-existing projects on Abel and Taito by the Norwegian (Oslo) and Finnish (Helsinki and Turku) NLPL members. These groups, for the time being at least, comprise the more experienced HPC users who in recent years have consumed up to one–two million core hours per year each. While NLPL remains in its start-up phase, these groups currently plan to continue using their ‘own’ (non-NLPL) allocations, meaning that NLPL usage may appear much smaller than the total HPC usage by Nordic language processing researchers.